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Omprakash Valmiki's *Joothan*: A Study of Dalit Resistance

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Abstract:

The term “Dalit” was first used by Ambedkar in 1928 in his journal of “Bahishkrit Bharat”. It was derived from Sanskrit ‘Dala’ means “crushed” or “broken to pieces”. Dalit literature is a distinctive literary form and it moves from personal struggle to universal appeal. Dalit literature came into existence in the 1960s when a group of Dalit writers took up their pen inspired by the message of Mahatma Jyotirao Phule and Dr.Ambedkar: “Don’t let your pen be restricted to your own questions” (Nimabalkar Waman 32). Dalit writings focus on the the theme of Dalit’s freedom and emancipation. It is an attempt to articulate voices among this marginalized class of people to come in action from their passivity and stillness. The Dalit literature’s journey from the margins to assertion, representation and resistance defines the change in the contours and borders of what Indian literature today is. The contemporary use of “Dalit” is centered on the idea by oppression, but they survive and even thrive by finding meaning in the struggle of their existence. My article proposes to analyse Omprakash Valmiki’s *Joothan* as resistance literature.

Keywords: Dalit, oppression, struggle, survival, resistance.

Introduction:

Joothan starts with an account of Valmiki's birth and upbringing as an untouchable (Chuhra or Bhangi) in caste – ridden society and goes to describe his story, particularly his early years as excruciatingly painful and charred by humiliating circumstances. He grew up in a social order that was extremely cruel and inhuman and unsympathetic towards Dalits. He writes “One can somehow get past poverty and deprivation but it is impossible to get past caste.” Valmiki relates how Dalits worked day in and out for a high – caste marriage in the village and had at the end to wait for *Joothan* (leftover meals and scraps of food) as their reward. Dalit autobiography is not just remembering of things past, but a shaping and restructuring of them in such a way as to help understand one's life and the social order that shaped it, on the one hand, and to arouse a passion for change in the Dalit reader on the other. Answering main – stream critics that Dalit literature is nothing but reportage, Dalit writers point to the authenticity of experience as being the most important characteristic of Dalit writing. *Joothan* is a bold resistance to the caste – ridden Hindu society.

Valmiki portrays the victim of the caste discrimination in *Joothan*:

“Caste is a very important element of Indian society. As soon as a person is born, “caste” determines his or her destiny. Being born is not in the control, then why would I have been born in a Bhangi household? Those who call themselves the standard bearers of this countries great cultural heritage, did they decide which homes they would be born into?”

(*Joothan* 18)

The caste discrimination in India is very deep rooted. Even the jails which are termed reformeries are not free of it. One of the most circulated news papers *The Times of India*

writes about many incidents of caste – based discriminations in jail. “Daulat Kunwar has been imprisoned several times. Once behind bars, it was the same story each time for this Dalit activist.”

Caste discrimination starts the moment an inmate steps into a prison. It is real and it has been going on for many years.

(The Times of India)

Daulat Kunwar says, “Dalits are mostly tasked with cleaning and sweeping if anyone refuses, he is beaten up by other inmates on the directions of the jail administration.” Another prisoner Ram Bahadur Singh recounts, Dalit inmates are often told to form separate queues for food. It is like feeding us the leftovers like animals”. Now Dalits in India’s jails see hope of better treatment following Supreme Court’s landmark order on October 3 striking down a series of “colonial era” rules mentioned in prison manuals across the country which “reinforced caste-based division of labour particularly targeting marginalized communities.” The recent apex court ruling has sparked optimism within police ranks too. UP DGP Prashant Kumar who hailed the decision told TOI “It’s a bold stride towards restoring the dignity of labour within Indian prisons. The verdict signals a long awaited dawn of justice. For centuries, caste and corruption were wrongly fused, reducing entire communities to lives of subjugation and indignity.” Additional district judge Shehzad Ali, Bulandshahr said, “The Supreme Court ruling will strengthen the hands of lawyers and activists to ensure compliance. We’ve visited jails regularly to address complaints. Now, we’ll ensure strict compliance and take immediate action against violations.”

Contextually we may discuss in brief *Karukku* (1992), the autobiography of Bama in Tamil. She wrote the work primarily as a means of dealing with the personal crisis that she faced after leaving the convent. She deals with the reasons for leaving the Order. A major

part of the work deals with the lives, labour, celebration, conflicts, beliefs, games and festivals of the members of her community who were converted to Christianity. She is successful in tracing the problems of the community and linking them to the caste practices that have seeped into all institutionalized religions in India.

Dalit Movement is the result of the constant apathy and hatred having been generated for centuries over the cruel, inhuman, even barbaric treatment of the so-called lower castes by the upper castes in India. Since Dalits were assigned the duties of serving the other three Varnas, they were deprived of even the basic human rights, they in the social hierarchy laid down in Manu Smriti; they were denied a socio-economic as well as political status in the scheme of things. This led to gross inequality, oppression and exploitation, as a result of which Dalits were excluded from the mainstream society and were only allowed to pursue menial occupations like carrying night soil, cleaning dry latrines, sweeping, scavenging, skinning dead cattle, etc.

Joothan is a memoir of growing-up "untouchable" in the 1950s outside a typical village in Uttar Pradesh. Told as a series of piercing vignettes, *Joothan* is a remarkable record of a rare Indian journey, one that took a boy from extremely wretched socioeconomic conditions to prominence as an author and social critic. Many Hindi writers and poets have written about the charms of village life, says Valmiki, but its "real truth", depicting the "terrible suffering of village life has not been touched upon by the epic poets of Hindi". In this he echoes Ambedkar's views: "What is a village but a sink of localism, a den of ignorance and narrow-mindedness?"

Valmiki was born into the Chuhra or Bhangi caste, whose ordained job it was to sweep the roads, clean the cattle barns, get shit off the floor, dispose of dead animals, work in the fields during harvests and perform other physical labour for upper-caste people, in this case the Taga or Tyagi Brahmins. The Tyagis didn't address them by name, only called out,

"Oe Chuhre" or "Abey Chuhre". It was alright to touch cows and stray dogs but touching a Chuhra caused instant "pollution". During Valmiki's boyhood, his entire family worked hard, yet they "didn't manage to get two decent meals a day", not the least because they often didn't get paid for their labour and instead "got sworn at and abused".

"There was muck strewn everywhere. The stench was so over- powering that one would choke within a minute. The pigs wandering in narrow lanes, naked children, dogs, daily fights, this was the environment of my childhood," says Valmiki. What Valmiki had going for him was a headstrong set of parents, determined to give him a better future. His father had a hard time getting him admitted into a government-run primary school. But the boy was not allowed to sit on the benches but on the floor, at the back by the door, from where he couldn't see the blackboard well. Other boys hurled epithets and beat him regularly, turning him into a cowering introverted kid. Even the teachers looked for excuses to punish him, "so that I would run away from the school and take up the work for which I was born." In the fourth grade, a new headmaster thrashed him almost daily and one day asked him to take a broom and sweep all the rooms and the playground in the school. On the third day when the boy quietly sneaked into his class, the headmaster pounced on him, dragged him out and threw him on the ground, ordering him to get back to the task of sweeping.

As it turned out, his father, who was passing by, saw him sweeping the playground. He snatched the broom and began screaming at the one who had asked his son to take up the menial work. The headmaster called his father and asked him to remove his son from the school. But his father challenged the headmaster that his son would study there, and more would be following him. With the help of a village elder, Valmiki was allowed to attend school, else he would have ended up illiterate like the rest of his family.

Joothan encapsulates the pain, humiliation and poverty of Valmiki's community, which not only had to rely on joothan, i.e., leftover meals or fermented scraps of food, but

also relished it. His community looked forward to marriage feasts in the village where they would gather outside with big baskets. After the guests had eaten, the dirty leaf plates were put in the Chuhra's baskets, which they took home, to save the joothan sticking to them. At the end of one such marriage feast, Valmiki's mother requested the Brahmin host for fresh food and sweets for her children, only to be humiliated and told to mind her place, be satisfied with what she had collected, and to get going. His mother was furious. She asked the host to pick up the joothan and serve it to his marriage guests the next morning. She never picked up joothan from the upper-caste houses after that.

As his family fell on hard times, Valmiki continued to face severe discrimination at school. Though he consistently did well in his studies, his memories of school are suffused with pain and humiliation: from taunts and beatings by schoolmates and teachers in a "terror-filled environment", to his exclusion from extra-curricular activities. During exams, he was not allowed to drink water from a glass when thirsty. He had to cup his hands and "the peon would pour water from way high up, lest our hands touch the glass." He feels that he has grown up in a "cruel and barbaric civilization", although he does fondly remember a couple of boys who didn't let caste come between them.

Remarkably enough, Valmiki was determined to make full use of his school library. By the time he reached eighth grade, he had read Premchand, Rabindranath Tagore and Saratchandra. He also read novels and short stories to his mother at home. This was the beginning of his literary sensibility. He was the first youngster from his community, not just from his 'basti' but from all the surrounding villages of his area to pass the high school exam. His elated father naturally organized a community feast to mark the occasion.

Unlike in the dominant Hindu tradition-which Valmiki denigrates and wants no part of-widow remarriage was even in the 1960s an accepted norm in his community. He describes in some detail how their gods were utterly different from the Hindu Brahminical

gods and how different their rituals were. Around Janmashtami, for instance, they worshipped not Krishna but Jaharpir, a folk deity, and "during Deepawali it is not the goddess Lakshmi but Mai Madaran who is worshipped and offered a piglet" and a bottle of liquor. He also describes lots of family drama and interpersonal politics in his community, not shying from reproach where it is due, acknowledging that the women got an even rawer deal than men.

Valmiki also recounts other changes that were beginning to take place in his village. The young men of his community had begun to refuse to work without wages. This soon escalated into an open confrontation with the upper-caste men who couldn't tolerate their nerve, and even got local police to beat them up. Valmiki calls this a turning point of sorts; young men began departing from their 'basti' to nearby towns and cities in search of employment.

"Dalit literature describes the world differently, from a Dalit perspective."(Raj Gauthaman) Its primary motive is the liberation of Dalits. Because of the anger against the age-old oppression, the expression of the Dalit writers has become sharp. Bama Faustina is one of the first Dalit Tamil writers to achieve international attention for her works. Her autobiography *Karukku* is a powerful portrayal of Dalit suppression. Revolving around the main theme of caste oppression within the Catholic Church, *Karukku* portrays the tension between the self and the community, and presents Bama's life as a process of self-reflection and recovery from social and institutional betrayal. Bama's re-reading and interpretation of the Christian scriptures as an adult enables her to carve out both a social vision and a message of hope for Dalits by emphasizing the revolutionary aspects of Christianity, the values of equality, social justice, and love towards all. Aswathy Mohan's paper, entitled "The Rise of the Falcon from the Limbo of Non-existence: A Reading of Bama's *Karukku*" aims at a study

of how Bama has attempted to reflect on the existential predicament of the Dalits, especially Dalit Christians, in her autobiography *Karukku*.

Mapping a new territory of Dalitness has to be perceived as an ordeal for any Dalit irrespective of the geographical boundaries which separated them from the elite. Seen as the upper caste Hindu's Other, Dalits, who are accorded spatial and normative inferiority, are positioned as objects of revulsion. Subalternised thus by birth and sanctified by sacred authority, the socio-political status of the Dalits which was supposed to be unalterable was challenged by Dalit intellectuals, writers and activists. An unromantic and un pitying echo of the materiality of Dalit life in all its dimensions which reverberates their Dalitness is what makes Dalit literature distinct from other Indian literatures.

Joothan, set in the Chuhra community in Barla village, which draws a panorama of the journey the author- narrator Omprakash Valmiki, embarks upon in his quest for the self- affirmation of the Dalits in general and the self-proclamation of himself as a Dalit. The image of the silenced subaltern being very normative in context, Valmiki by recounting his traumatic past not only testifies his experience but also becomes a subject in the process. Valmiki asserts his subjective formation through a series of flashbacks into his early childhood. Born as a Chuhra, Valmiki finds that the chances are at odds for him in order to climb up the ladder of acceptability and recognition.

Recounting the harsh realities, the Dalit women of Mahar community had to endure, Baby Kamble posits *The Prisons We Broke* as the representational voice of disagreement and assertion by a subalternised Dalit woman. Interrogating the denied spaces of socio-politico-cultural rendezvous for the Dalits, Kamble records events of her childhood in her maternal village which depicted the alienated world of the Mahar community.

Untouchability, a social evil propagated and exercised by the upper caste, defines the Othering of the Dalits in terms of purity, pollution, rejection, revulsion, discrimination etc.

Nevertheless, the untouchable Other perceive the very same practice of untouchability, which encompasses "experiences of exclusion, subjugation, dispossession and oppression" (Limbale 11), as the essence of the Dalit materiality. By giving voice to the authentic Dalit experience through the careful chronicling of the day to day experience, the speaking subaltern serves a radical role whereby the purity of the 'savarna' space is destroyed and re- configured.

Mapping the very essence of Dalitness is what exactly resonates in *Joothan* and *The Prisons We Broke*. The author- narrators, undertake a panoramic journey visualizing and revisiting the memories of childhood which was wrought with suffering, pain, humiliation as well as an unarticulated desire to be the subject. A microscopic view offered by the narrators provides ample self-attestation as well as authentication of their collective experience. Valmiki recounts the humiliating experiences at his school, where to his knowledge he finds that a hidden apartheid was functional in the socio-cultural space the Dalits occupied there.

Filled with the desire to be the subject, a speaking subaltern, Valmiki wanted to transcend the class and caste consciousness through education as Ambedkar himself had requested the Dalits to attain. Valmiki was often made to stand on the margins as a spectator even though he was extremely good in his studies. His frustration at being the outsider or the Other even in the space of knowledge makes him question not only the upper caste superiority but also the unaccountable ritualistic observances in his own community. The Chuhra are constantly reminded of their pathetic fate thus, "However much you study... you will still remain a Chuhra" (32).

The transformatory as well as liberatory aspects in Valmiki was effectualized at Tyagi Inter College where Valmiki embraces the image of a radical Dalit activist. Realizing that there won't be any change in the way a Chuhra or a Dalit is treated, Valmiki persists in his urge to fight the cultural hegemony of the upper caste by retaining his surname as Valmiki in order to establish the distinct Dalitness in every way. His fight was against the Othered

spaces and identities which he was able to challenge and subvert through the rejection of the hegemonic space. Valmiki's father who was passing by, saw the humiliation and exploitation of his son confronted the headmaster. He screamed, "Who is the teacher, that progeny of Dronacharya, who forces my son to sweep?" In another instance of shame and humiliation, Valmiki relates how Dalits worked day in and out for a high-caste marriage in the village and had at the end to wait for joothan (leftover meals and scraps of food and sweets) as their reward.

During a wedding, when the guests and the 'baratis', the bridegroom's party, were eating their meals, the Chuhras would sit outside with big baskets. After the baratis had eaten, the dirty pattals or leaf-plates were put in the Chuhras' baskets, which they took home, with the joothan sticking to them. The little pieces of pooris, bits of sweetmeats, and a little bit of vegetable were enough to make them happy. The joothan was eaten with a lot of relish... During the marriage season, our elders narrated, in thrilled voices, stories of baratis who had left several months of joothan.

Untouchability was abolished in 1949 but Dalits are still victims of prejudice, economic deficiency, aggression and mockery. Valmiki attacks the varna system and Brahminical rule with sternness. *Joothan* tries to create human feelings by connecting the pain and struggle of the Dalit with the feelings of the readers. Valmiki is of the opinion that even if India has progressed in many counts but the situation of Dalit remains the same. *Joothan* is a record of Valmiki's bitter experiences he has faced in his life. It is a series of piercing vignettes and is also a remarkable record of a rare Indian journey that a boy undertook from extremely wretched socio – economic condition to prominence as an author and social critic.

Conclusion:

The caste discrimination in Hinduism has doomed the glory of it over the years and it remains as a great thorn and mystery in the heart of mother India. The *Rig Veda* talks about four castes like the Brahmins, the Ksyatriyas, the Vaisyas and the Shudras. There is another class which does not come under the above mentioned classification and this is the “Untouchables.” The “Untouchables” are the victims of injustice, social inequality and deprived from enjoying the basic human rights. Etymologically the word Dalit refers to such signifiers as downtrodden, deprived, disadvantaged, underprivileged, abused, marginalized, humbled etc. Today a new scenario is emerging. With more and more classes clamouring to be included into the circle of SCs and OBCs, the Dalit class itself is losing its caste constitution. This is especially true since some categories of Sikhs and Christians have raised the demand of being identified as backward and in need of reservation. Further, the increasing access of Dalits to education and employment has raised the possibility of the creation of a “Creamy Layer” within the Dalit class itself and the Supreme Court of India in its recent remark has endorsed this opinion. The author – narrator in *Jhoothan* challenges and attempts to transcend the established notions of invisibility. The radicalness with which the narrative puts forth his unflinching experiences of the deconstruction of the Brahminical space enables the narrative to be termed rightly as liberatory and revolutionary. The resistant selfhood which Valmiki is able to assert, openly avows her desire to have an individuality of his own by denouncing the cultural expectations of the upper caste as well as his own community. Mapping a new territory of Dalitness has to be perceived as an ordeal for any Dalit irrespective of the geographical boundaries which separated them from the elite. Seen as the upper caste Hindu's Other, Dalits, who are accorded spatial and normative inferiority, are positioned as objects of revulsion. Subalternised thus by birth and sanctified by sacred authority, the socio-political status of the Dalits which was supposed to be unalterable was

challenged by Dalit intellectuals, writers and activists. An unromantic and unpitying echo of the materiality of Dalit life in all its dimensions which reverberates their Dalitness is what makes Dalit literature distinct from other Indian literatures. Dalit literature has come up as a cultural revolution all over India. This literature is not about sympathy but it is all about fellow – feeling. Our nation will grow if it preaches of no discrimination on the basis of caste along side secularism. This discrimination has weakend our national integrity and though it is late we all must strive for a new India free from the narrowness of caste, creed and colour because we all know that united we stand divided we fall.

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